

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATION IN LEARNING LEXICAL UNITS

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада лугавий бирликларни ўрганишда мулоқотнинг аҳамияти ва янги ҳосил бўлиши мумкин бўлган лугавий бирликлар жараёни ҳақида ёзилган. Бундан ташқари уларнинг турлари ҳақида маълумотлар келтириб ўтилган.

Калим сўзлар: Лексик бирликлар, тил, ўргатиш, ижтимоий, ўрганиш, усуллар, муҳит, жараён, салбий таъсир, товушлар, транспозиция, билим, кўникма, малака, алоқа.

Аннотация. В этой статье обсуждается важность общения при изучении словарных единиц и процесс формирования новых словарных единиц. Кроме того, дана информация об их видах.

Ключевые слова: Лексические единицы, язык, обучение, социальное, обучение, методы, окружающая среда, процесс, негативное влияние, звуки, транспозиция, знания, навыки, компетентность, общение.

Abstract. This article discusses the importance of communication in the study of vocabulary items and the process by which new vocabulary items can be formed. In addition, information about their types is given.

Keywords: Lexical units, language, teach, social, learn, methods, environment, process, negative influence, sounds, transposition, knowledge, skills, competence, communication.

New lexical units are an important source of enrichment of English vocabulary. Their scope is extremely wide and includes from stylistically neutral, general literary units to slang vulgarisms. Lack of in-depth study of lexical and phraseological stylistics, the border of different functional styles, as well as the frequent changes in the norms of word usage create serious difficulties in determining the stylistic status of lexical units. Moreover, the new lexical system cannot be called stable, because it cannot keep pace with the language system, and therefore needs constant semantic-stylistic correction.

In world linguistics, the problem of continuous innovation processes in the language system has never lost its relevance. Especially in the last decades of the 20th century and the first decades of the 21st century, there were sharp changes, radical changes, and unprecedented updates in various aspects of social life. Extra linguistic factors such as the reunification of Germany, the establishment of the European Union, the rapid development of information and communication technologies. The processes of globalization and integration have led to the acceleration of innovative processes in the vocabulary of the English language, the enrichment of the language through lexical units, because of which their special study has become a more urgent issue.

Currently, in world linguistics, research is being conducted in the directions of researching lexical units, which are considered the main source of language development, in semantic-derivative, integrative, linguo-cultural, semantic-communicative, linguo-cognitive, functional-pragmatic, psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic aspects.

Despite the fact that studies are being carried out on issues such as the role of everyday colloquial speech in the current English language system. The specific features of the development of its vocabulary, the creation of new lexical units through non-standard methods, and their variability, there are unclear situations and aspects that need to be studied regarding the research of lexical units within the framework of colloquial speech. Expressiveness, emotionality, imagery,

evaluation, etc., are important problems, because their solution provides an opportunity for a deeper study of the fundamental issues of the new lexical meaning. Also, while explaining the essence of new lexical units, the specificity of their semantics and the mechanisms of their creation, the process of the emergence of lexical units, the research methods of lexical and phraseological materials of different styles, it creates a basis for the comprehensive study of the new lexicon in texts and dictionaries.

The relevance of this issue is determined by studying the pragmatic factors of speech activity.

In world linguistics, innovative processes in the language system are widely studied based on the materials of different languages. During the past period, M.D. Stepanova, V.D. Devkin, E.V. Rosen, M.I. Umarchodzaev, B.T. Ganeev, I. Ibrahimkhodzhaev, S.I. Alatorseva, S.I. Toshalieva, W.Fleischer, P.Brown, R.Baayen, B.Gardin and others were involved.

Now, issues such as the description of lexical units in a number of functional styles of the language have already attracted the attention of linguists, and research in this regard continues, but the issue of "renaming" concepts that have taken a firm place in the lexical system is not sufficiently covered in linguistic sources. Lexical innovations are studied in depth in studies devoted to functional-stylistic analysis of new lexical material. In addition, it is necessary to identify productive word formation methods that enrich the colloquial lexicon with new lexical units, as well as to study some types of semantic processes that lead to the formation of new colloquial meanings.

Each type of communication requires a specific situation. In fact, written mass communication is characterized by a communication situation in which the participants of the dialogue perform through a specific speech object. As a result, this type of communication takes the form of indirect communication, which is further complicated by the distance of the participants in terms of space and time and the presence of an intermediary person. The mediator plays an important role in the communicative act of written mass communication. For example, in written advertisements that are constantly used in everyday life, a copywriting bureau is an intermediary. The intermediary receives the relevant content information from the advertiser.

The third feature of the external-relational aspect of the complex dynamic system of the language is combined with the second, that is, the use of the complex dynamic system of the language in the process of speech communication in accordance with the customs and norms of the community. The internal-structural aspect of the complex dynamic system of the language covers the concept of language as a construction system. Special attention is paid to the analysis of system elements and construction models of system elements and a system of relations. Special attention is paid to the study of connections of system elements. The following features characterize this aspect:

- 1) Integrity of the language system and the fact that language construction is not completely dependent on some changes in material existence;
- 2) Differences between language system elements and their actual signs;
- 3) Interaction and influence of language elements at the same level;
- 4) Development of inter level communication and relations;
- 5) Structural changes of construction models of language elements. It is distinguished by taking into account the communication process from all sides, paying attention to speech creativity, the language and style of the "speech work", and the interaction between individuals in the exchange of information through the medium of language. At the same time, also a consistency

envisages scientific research related to the generalization of the new lexicon and the study of new meaning features in the communicative act, which is one of the important areas in the aspects of general language practice.

In conclusion, communication is a social activity and belongs to the system of types of purposeful human activity. Therefore, it is a social phenomenon in terms of its occurrence, nature, development laws. The purpose of communication is social communication, which tends to influence society. In this way, the characteristic of human communication is determined. Relative completeness of thought in terms of content and grammar, in general, is the basis of any conscious communication. The main condition for the use of any language unit is its completeness in terms of form and content. This completeness is ensured by the legal connections of independent and auxiliary words. The first unit of language studied in the communicative aspect is the thought, which is the reason for its recognition as the initial category of any linguistic analysis. The interrelationship of language units is precisely the context that occurs simultaneously with the process of formation of each word, construction and thought. The use of any language unit requires the description of its immediate environment. In particular, it is required to analyze the complete thought as the smallest communicative link and device at the layer of the phrase.

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